

Response of rice and wheat to zinc fertilization in alkali soils

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Large areas of alkali land in the Indo-Gangetic plains are not cultivated. At the Gudda experimental farm, CSSRI, we evaluated responses to Zn application of rice and wheat on an alkali soil with pH 10.45, EC 4.08 dS/m, 94% exchangeable sodium percentage, 3.73% CaCO₃, 20% clay, 26% silt, 54% sand, 28 t gypsum requirement/ha, and 0.44 ppm DTPA-Zn.

Zero, 10, 20, 40, 80, and 120 kg ZnSO₄/ha were applied in a randomized block design with 4 replications, and 14 t gypsum/ha was surface broadcast and mixed in the upper 8-10 cm soil. Jaya rice and HD2009 wheat were grown in

Effect of Zn on the yield and Zn uptake by rice and wheat crops in alkali soil, Karnal, India.

ZnSO ₄ added (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)						Zn uptake (g/ha)				DTPA-Zn (ppm) after		
	Rice			Wheat			Rice		Wheat		Wheat	Rice	
	1980	1981	1982	1983	1980-81	1981-82	1982-83	1980	1983	1980-81	1982-83	1982-83	1983
0	5.1	5.0	6.6	5.0	1.2	1.4	2.0	144	151	28	41	0.44	0.41
10	6.0	6.1	7.5	6.0	1.6	2.2	2.9	198	302	66	105	1.87	2.06
20	6.0	5.8	7.7	6.2	1.7	2.4	2.9	221	319	73	129	3.09	3.54
40	6.0	5.9	7.5	6.1	1.6	2.2	3.1	235	273	79	139	6.05	7.00
80	6.0	5.7	7.5	6.2	1.7	2.3	3.1	244	407	108	163	10.95	12.58
120	6.0	5.7	7.5	6.1	1.6	2.4	3.0	253	414	113	193	15.45	18.13
CD (0.05)	0.61	0.62	0.67	0.26	0.36	0.60	0.32	25	29	7	22	.66	.89

sequence. ZnSO₄ and 75 kg N/ha as urea were applied basally and the remaining 75 kg N/ha was topdressed in 2 equal splits 3 and 6 wk after planting.

Rice plants in the Zn control plots were stunted and had visible Zn deficiency symptoms. Grain yield and Zn uptake by rice and wheat crops were significantly

less in the control than in Zn-treated plots.

Applying 10 kg ZnSO₄/ha significantly increased available Zn and grain yield of both crops (see table). Applying 20 to 120 kg ZnSO₄/ha did not increase yield over that with 10 kg ZnSO₄.

Responses of rice to some trace elements

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We evaluated the effect of trace elements Zn, Cu, Fe, and Mn on yield at the Government Seed Farm Rakh Mangan, D. I. Khan, Northwest Frontier Province, Pakistan. Treatments were no fertilizer (control), NPK, NPKZn, NPKCu, NPKFe, NPKMn, NPKZnCu, and NPKFeMn. Zn, Cu, Fe, and Mn were applied at 5.0, 5.0, 2.5, and 2.5 kg/ha. NPK at 120, 40, and 50 kg/ha was applied as urea, single superphosphate, and potassium sulfate. Experiments were on two clay soils. One had pH 8.0, 11% CaCO₃, 0.79% organic matter, and 3 ppm Olsen's available P. The other had pH 8.2, 13% CaCO₃, 0.81% organic matter, and 3 ppm Olsen's available P.

With Cu and Fe application, yield increased more than 10% over NPK alone. There was some yield response to Zn and Mn, but the increase was not statistically significant (see table). Our preliminary studies show the soils are Cu and Fe deficient either in absolute quantity or in availability to rice.

Effect of trace elements on rice yield, Peshawar, Pakistan.

Treatment	Trace ^a element	Paddy yield ^b (t/ha)		Increase (%) over NPK
		1982	1983	
0-0-0	O	5.3 c	5.1 f	—
120-40-50	O	7.4 c	6.5 e	—
120-40-50	Zn	7.7 ab	6.6 de	3.2
120-40-50	Cu	8.7 ab	6.9 cde	12.0
120-40-50	Fe	7.8 ab	7.7 ab	12.0
120-40-50	Mn	7.8 ab	6.8 cde	5.8
120-40-50	Zn+Cu	8.8 a	7.2 bc	15.4
120-40-50	Fe+Mn	8.0 ab	8.0 a	15.4
120-40-50	Zn+Cu+Fe+Mn	—	7.1 cd	—

^aZn = 5 kg/ha, Cu = 5 kg/ha, Fe = 2.5 kg/ha, Mn = 2.5 kg/ha. ^bMeans followed by similar letters do not differ significantly at 5% level.

Relative efficiency of simple and complex fertilizers for rice

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We compared the effects of simple and complex fertilizers on the yield of IRRI-6 on 2 soils at the Agricultural Research Station, Dera Ismail Khan, Northwest Frontier Province of Pakistan, in 1982 and 1983. Fertilizers were urea (46%N), urea plus single superphosphate (SSP

(8.8% P), urea plus diammonium phosphate (DAP) (18% N and 20% P), and urea plus nitrophos (NP) (23% N and 10% P). N and P rates were 120 and 40 kg/ha. Soil was a clay loam with pH 7.9, 16.0% CaCO₃, and 6 ppm Olsen's available P in 1982. In 1983, the soil had pH 8.2, 18.5% CaCO₃, and 11.5 ppm Olsen's available P.

Applying urea plus DAP produced better yields than urea plus NP. The urea plus DAP treatment yielded highest in 1982 (see table), but yields were similar in 1983. In 1983, urea plus DAP pro-